

DESIGNING THE LEAST-COST MINI-GRID SOLUTION FOR THE LALA COMMUNITY

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Executive Summary

This report presents a techno-economic analysis of mini-grid electrification for the off-grid Lala Community in Ghana's Bono East Region using RAMP and MicroGridsPy modeling tools. The study assesses two key scenarios: No Capacity Expansion (NCE) and Capacity Expansion (CE), each simulating energy demand growth, renewable energy penetration levels, and system performance over a 5-year period. Key findings indicate that while NCE results in oversized systems with high upfront costs and underutilized assets, the CE scenario enables scalable, cost-effective investments aligned with actual demand growth. In both cases, increasing renewable energy penetration reduced reliance on diesel generators but raised levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) due to higher capital investments in solar PV and batteries.

It is recommended that adopting a phased investment strategies is best to improve resource utilization and effective performance or efficiency of energy technologies. Also prioritizing on accurate demand projections and productive-use development is key to optimizing mini-grid design.

1. Introduction

African countries still face challenges in accessing reliable and affordable electricity. As of 2023, Ghana has an electricity access rate of 88.85% (Ministry of Finance, 2024), with a majority of the unelectrified areas being off-grid and island communities. These unelectrified areas, limited or no access, hinder education, healthcare, socio-economic

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activities and the quality of life. Currently, Ghana does not have a specific regulatory framework for the development of mini-grids, however, the Renewable Energy Act 2011 (Act 832) and the Renewable Energy Master Plan both support the development of mini-grids as a solution for rural areas (off-grid and remote communities). Mini-grid development in Ghana is a public-led initiative, where the Ministry of Energy and Green Transition seeks funding or grants for private developers to develop the mini-grid, which is later handed over to a government utility to manage and operate.

This case study focuses on the Lala Community, which is located in the Sene East District of the Bono East Region. This community is one of the island settlements included in the government of Ghana's plan to develop 35 mini-grids across 60 communities (African Development Bank, 2023; Danish Energy Management, 2023). The Lala Community has a total population of 562, with a household count of 158. Lala is low low-income community with their socio-economic activities being fishing, fish processing (smoking and drying) and small scale farming.

Planning and managing the energy supply to fulfil present and future demand sustainably and economically becomes crucial as the population steadily increases and income levels change. This case study applies the application of RAMP to generate the load demand and MicroGridsPy modelling tool to analyze and simulate energy demand, system design and electrification impacts in the Lala Community. The study considers the socio-economic structure and energy usage patterns to understand different user classes and their specific energy needs, to provide a comprehensive energy optimization model design for the strategic planning and operational management of mini-grid systems at the minimum cost.

2. Methodology

This case study applies the utilization of Renewable Energy Access and Modeling Platform (RAMP) to determine the load demand of the community, taking into consideration certain parameters such as the income levels, appliance use and productive-use. The second modelling tool is Microgridspy, which depends on the hourly profile of the energy needs simulated in RAMP. Microgridspy optimizes the various forms of energy to assist in the planning and operation of mini-grid for the Lala Community.

Figure 1: Six (6) Phases of the Comprehensive Energy Solution Planning (CESP) Framework

Data was sourced from published reports, national statistics and articles online. These data provided informed information on the estimated population size, number of households, income levels and productive-use trends. The annual growth rate for rural areas in Ghana is 0.4%, and therefore, the population in Lala was assumed to increase at a study growth rate of 0.4% per year, from 562 in year 1 to approximately 573 in year 5.

Using these assumptions, RAMP was used to generate an hourly load profile for year 1, 3 and 5. The aggregated hourly load (aggregated) was projected to increase at a rate of approximately 165.48% between the 2nd year and the 3rd year as a result of the introduction of a high-income tier and small enterprise (productive-use) by year 3. Productive-use of appliances such as deep freezers increased the load demand significantly and assists in streamlining the peak demand during the day. However, the aggregated load demand projected for the 4th and 5th year, had a slight increase rate of 5.24%.

Two major scenarios were evaluated to determine the impact of renewable energy penetration on the levelized cost of electricity and total investment cost. Below are the scenarios exploited:

- No Capacity Expansion (NCE): This scenario is the baseline, which focuses on assessing how much the total energy demand over 5 years could be met using renewable energy without adding any new generation or storage capacity. Constraints (e.g., 70%, 60%, 50%, 40% and no constraints) are applied to know the penetration levels of renewable energy to determine the best penetration level with the least levelized cost of electricity.

- Capacity Expansion (CE): This scenario also assesses the total energy demand over 5 years, however, it allows new generation and storage capacity to be added over time. The model also investigates the feasibility of achieving varying degrees of renewable energy penetration (e.g., 70%, 60%, 50%, 40% and no constraints) within 5 years of simulation.

3. Results

BASE SCENARIO – NO CAPACITY EXPANSION							
Renewable Penetration (%)	LCOE (USD/kWh)	PV (kW)	Battery (kWh)	Genset (kW)	NPC (kUSD)	Total Investment (kUSD)	Minimum Penetration Rate (%)
88.35	0.7189	60	207	13	168.26	177.45	70
80.72	0.6	51	150	14	140.42	140.46	60
73.36	0.495	40	108	14	115.87	108.23	50
57.18	0.4169	30	71	19	97.57	81.13	40
4.11	0.2715	1	0	33	63.55	21.16	0

Table 1: Summary Results of No Capacity Expansion Scenario

SCENARIO – CAPACITY EXPANSION (2 INVESTMENT STEPS)							
Renewable Penetration (%)	LCOE (USD/kWh)	PV (kW)	Battery (kWh)	Genset (kW)	NPC (kUSD)	Total Investment (kUSD)	Minimum Penetration Rate (%)
85	0.5793	42-59	140 – 218	13 -13	135.58	150.01	70
76.58	0.4915	35 – 49	103 – 166	14 – 14	115.03	119.47	60
61.11%	0.4177	28 – 39	68 – 117	14 – 14	97.77	91.2	50
46.75%	0.3565	21 – 29	41 – 90	16 – 16	83.44	69.91	40
16.30%	0.2627	1 – 20	0 – 64	20 – 20	61.49	39.1	0

Table 2: Summary Results of Capacity Expansion Scenario

- In both scenarios, the renewable energy penetration increases as the constraints (from no constraints to 70%), resulting in a decline of diesel generation because more energy is provided by the solar PV and stored in the batteries. Also, the levelized cost of electricity rises because larger solar PV systems and more batteries

are required for high renewable energy shares, which raises the upfront cost. This further requires large amounts of money for developing renewable energy infrastructure and therefore the total investment cost increases.

- The results of the no capacity expansion scenario show an oversized system with low energy demand in the early years. This is because the system was planned to satisfy the energy needs of the entire 5 years. Additionally, the energy technologies (solar PV, battery storage and diesel generators) are underutilized, leading to inefficiencies that increase the levelized cost of electricity and the total investment cost. Applying a high minimum renewable energy penetration constraints lessens the dependency on diesel generators. The consumption of fuel also is decreased by more renewable energy penetration. Overall, the scenario illustrates the need for phased investment plans to guarantee long-term economic viability and ideal asset use.
- In the capacity expansion scenario, growing demand and productive-use development is enabled to expand the system over time by adding extra solar PV, batteries and genset capacity. In contrast, the capacity expansion scenario allows the efficient utilization of the energy technologies and avoids early oversizing by upgrading the system in the 3rd year, when income levels and productive-use applications are implemented. Greater investments are made in solar PV and batteries as the use of renewable energy grows and hence, lessens the need for diesel generators. Long-term sustainability and effective use of energy sources are guaranteed in the phased design even though the total investment cost and levelized cost of electricity rises with high renewable energy shares.

Figure 2: Effect of Renewable Energy Penetration of LCOE - No Capacity Expansion Scenario

Figure 3: Effect of Renewable Energy Penetration of LCOE - Capacity Expansion Scenario

The results shows increasing renewable energy penetration corresponds to a decrease in diesel generation resulting in a increase in the levelized cost of electricity. However, the levelized cost of electricity for the capacity expansion scenario is lower than that of the no capacity expansion scenario.

4. Discussion

Policy Recommendation

The government of Ghana should encourage or develop policies for incremental investment and financial models that allows upgrading of renewable energy infrastructure in mini-grid selected communities (off-grid and island communities) with gradual growing demand such as the Lala Community.

Insights and Results Implications

Excessive system sizing to accommodate future demand results in underutilized assests, inefficiencies and increase total investment cost and levelized cost in the no capacity expansion scenario. High minimum restrictions on renewable energy penetration significantly increases investment in solar PV and battery storage and hence increases the capital cost.

Early oversizing is prevented in the capacity expansion scenario and more economical in resource utilization is achieved by gradual system expansion based on actual demand increase. Also, the long-term sustainability is possible by phased investments which minizes

the capital and operation costs while lowering reliance on gensets. The levelized cost of electricity for the capacity expansion scenario is less as compared with the no capacity expansion.

Potential Areas for Future Research

Research into policy and financing models is needed to guarantee long-term energy access and phased renewable energy investments.

5. Conclusion

In summary, this study compares the no capacity expansion and capacity expansion scenarios for planning the development of a mini-grid in the Lala Community. The capacity expansion approach demonstrates the benefits of phased system sizing to meet actual demand leading to long-term sustainability and better resource utilization.

The results suggest that planning energy systems for off-grid or rural areas should consider scalability with flexible or phased financial models. The study also emphasizes on the significance of demand forecasting and the integration of storage solutions to address long-term energy needs.

Future research should explore hybrid renewable systems, advanced storage technologies, and financing mechanisms to further optimize off-grid energy solutions, ensuring both affordability and resilience in the transition to sustainable energy.

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